

**Organization of the teaching process using modern pedagogical technologies
in the field of pedagogy.**

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Abstract: Conclusions and suggestions on increasing the role of modern pedagogical technologies in the development of pedagogic science have been developed and the role of modern pedagogical technologies in the development of pedagogic science has been highlighted.

Key words: science of pedagogy, modern pedagogical technologies, pedagogical activity.

INTRODUCTION: among the activities necessary to implement for the organization and development of two-level higher education in the "Continuous education system and types" section of the national personnel training program of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "students using new pedagogical and information technology "Intensification of education, individualization of education and the development and adoption of distance education system technologies" are mentioned. The implementation of these activities will improve teaching, that is, the wide application of pedagogical technology to the educational process, the use of computerized automated teaching systems, the use of new technical and didactic tools and multimedia opportunities in education, distance learning It is done by

using modern teaching technologies, such as the introduction of language. In developed countries, new pedagogical technology was gradually formed and began to enter the Republic of Uzbekistan. The new pedagogical technology encourages students to think independently and work freely during the lesson.

In recent years, well-known pedagogic scientists and teachers of our Republic have been conducting effective research on the introduction of pedagogical technology into the educational process. The concept of pedagogical technology is also reflected in scientific articles, periodicals, topics and reports at conferences. In particular, scientists of our republic R.Kh. Jorayev. A.P. Parpiev, N.Kh. Saydahmedov, U.N. Nishonaliev, L. Farberman, L.V. Golish, U.Kh. Tolipov, and Russian pedagogic scientists V.P. Bezpalko, M.V.Klarin, V.M.Monakhov, P.I.Pidkasistii, as well as M.J. Aristanov, J.S. Khaidarov and others from Kazakhstan scientists tried to reveal the essence and importance of the concept of "pedagogical technology" in their scientific research. Currently, in pedagogical literature, lectures and official documents on educational problems, such as "new pedagogical technology", "advanced pedagogical technology", "modern pedagogical technology", "teaching technology", "educational technology" expressions are widely used. But these concepts are still not standardized and explained in encyclopedias. A single definition of the meaning of these expressions has not been developed, and therefore there are many different definitions of them. According to V. Guzev, the educational goals in the traditional method are vague in accordance with the requirements of the program, that is, they are characterized by a vague imagination wrapped in the concept of "mastery" of the learners. Educational processes are organized based on the generalization of work experiences of teachers

who have achieved more achievements. For each specific situation, the pedagogical activity of these teachers is shown as an example. But a number of scientists point out that the era of separate educational methods has passed and generalization of the experiences of any advanced pedagogues does not allow to build a systematic and goal-oriented, effective education. Today, many specialists criticize traditional pedagogy and emphasize that the approach in teaching is still based on the study of general concepts, rules and laws. Students' engagement with real-world objects is limited in scope and content.

It is known that any technology is based on the educational principles that form the new content of education and is aimed at educating the learner's personality, creating labor and professional skills in certain areas. The active subjects of the educational process are the teacher and the students, and their collaborative activities provide an opportunity for in-depth acquisition of theoretical and practical knowledge on a specific subject (or the basics of subjects) with little effort and time spent. In contrast to the methodical development of the educational process aimed at the active, effective activity of the teacher, pedagogical technologies aimed at activating and accelerating the educational process are focused on learners, as well as their personal and joint development with the teacher. In addition to creating conditions for mastering educational material taking into account their activity, education aims to systematically develop the activity and curiosity of students throughout the training, allows for quick involvement of pedagogical technology requirements in educational or production activities based on the creation of educational factors. Otherwise, weak, poorly understood, or poorly defined tasks can lead to ineffective completion of training.

The advantages of lessons organized on the basis of interactive pedagogical technologies are that such a system of lessons serves as the basis of science that sharpens thinking, forms boundless love for the Motherland, loyalty, civic ethics and democratic culture. Methods such as "Working with groups", "Discussion", "Problem teaching", "Brainstorming", as well as working with tables, writing works expressing independent opinion, and writing essays in the teaching of subjects increase the activity of students. Such lessons conducted on the basis of these methods save time, deliver new knowledge to the student, therefore, at the same time, they make the child think, encourage deep observation, attract all attention, problem situations, debates. he will be able to get out of the situation with the right conclusions in disputes, and will be able to connect and summarize the knowledge he has received with other topics.

The current educational development has brought a new direction - innovative pedagogy to the field. The term "innovative pedagogy" and related research appeared in Western Europe and the United States in the 60s. The socio-psychological aspect of innovation was developed by the American innovator E. Rogers. He studies the classification of categories (types) of the participants of the innovation process, their attitude to the innovation, their readiness to perceive it. Pedagogical technology — studies the problems of applying modern pedagogical technologies in the process of education and training, improving the effectiveness of the process of education and training based on the technological approach. Turning to the dictionary meaning of the word technology, this word is derived from the Greek "technos" - skill, art "logos" - teaching, science. means nos. It follows that the word technology is added to other terms and fulfills the tasks of developing this

field and improving its skills. The organization of the teaching process in innovative ways, that is, modern pedagogical technologies from the period of primary education, is highly effective in the educational system. This means that primary education is the foundation of general secondary education. Building this foundation in a solid way will facilitate the transition of educational processes in future periods.

CONCLUSION: In conclusion, it is reasonable to say that pedagogical technologies established from primary education serve as the first stage in the formation of subsequent periods of education. One of the important conditions for the formation of students' interest in learning can be the creation of an emotional situation, the need to learn and the development of conscious thinking. Activity is included in the structure of cognitive activity of students, that is, it is such work activity in which intellectual, volitional, emotional processes that enliven cognitive activity are manifested together. For active cognitive activity, comprehensive, deep interest in knowledge, specific effort, attention, and mental and physical forces necessary to achieve the set goal should be directed. Cognitive activity is individual, it is not an innate ability of a person, but it is formed in the process of his actions. Our children are our future, it is important to provide quality education in raising the next generation. Through modern pedagogical training, we can provide quality education to our children. I believe that we can increase their interest in learning.

(References):

1. J. Yoldoshev, S. Usmanov, "Basics of pedagogical technology", T., 2004.
2. J. Yoldoshev, "Education is on the way to renewal", T., 2000.

3. Ptiyukov V. Yu., "Osnov pedagogicheskoy tekhnologi", M., 1999. 4. Kadirova, M. (2020). The content of work on the formation of the behavior of minors. Archive Nauchnyx Publication JSPI.